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SHAPING A NEW FUTURE? ENGINEERING STUDENTS' PERCEPTION ABOUT INTERDISCIPLINARY SUSTAINABILITY COURSES

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this paper is to investigate the relevance and efficiency of interdisciplinary sustainability courses. These sustainability courses are designed for engineering students at Master level requiring the use of technical and sustainability skills and competences in the framework of project based learning.

We applied a mixed quantitative and qualitative methodology. First, we carried out a short quantitative survey (n=79) to investigate students' perception about the significance of sustainability courses, the developed skills and competences or the relevance of applied teaching and learning approach. After, we conducted a qualitative study with a group discussion about diverse questions for a deeper comprehension of students' view.

Our findings show a positive consideration of interdisciplinary approach viewed as particularly useful and relevant for addressing sustainable issues. Furthermore, sustainability courses develop numerous transversal skills and competences required for future sustainability achievements. In addition, by enhancing students' sustainability knowledge and awareness they were considered as impactful for students' future actions in their personal and professional life.

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1 INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest of sustainable education for engineering students due to a collective awareness of the importance of sustainable development for our future that we can observe in the requirements of the accreditation processes of the CTI (Commission des Titres d'Ingénieur – French engineering degree accreditation body) in France. When we decided to develop a new sustainability education module for our first year Master level engineering students (from Physics engineering and Electronics engineering), we were highly motivated to work on diverse sustainability issues closely related to our technical domains but rarely discussed before with our students.

These sustainability courses (2 ECTS), applying two different pedagogical approaches, were spread over two semesters. At the beginning, we applied a traditional lecture based teaching approach consisting 20% of the courses (6 hours of lectures) presenting different sustainable development topics (e. g.: 'Global citizenship and individual impact on sustainability development', 'Quantitative evaluation and comparison of mobility devices', etc.). We defined the principal learning objective of these traditional lectures as the rising of students' sustainability knowledge, awareness and curiosity.

Subsequently, we applied a Project Based Learning (PBL) teaching and learning approach for the 80% of these courses. Students were asked to work in group of ten and set up their team. It was very unusual for them as they are used to work in small teams (composed only of two or three students) and often have no choice to select their team members. They had the opportunity to choose their subjects from a predefined list or propose their own subject according to their interest.² As a specific instruction, students had to follow a scientific approach and avoid any ideological approach. During their working sessions, they had the possibility to work with students from other disciplines and benefit from the coaching of professors. The project output consisted in the organization of a round table and the creation of a maximum 10 minutes long video including exclusively certified data. The assessment of the project work took place in a framework of a peer-evaluation.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Despite the overall recognition of the value and significance of interdisciplinarity in sustainability education, the implementation of interdisciplinary courses remains an important challenge for educators. According to a recent study of Van den Beemt et al. [1], the training of socially aware engineers and improvement of disciplinary programs are between the most emerging motivations of interdisciplinary engineering education. However, several barriers (like the lack of support, the complexity and diversity of interdisciplinary courses or the existing disciplinary

² For giving some example, the following subjects were chosen : 'Benefits and impacts of the digital world', 'Oil free mobility', 'Water management in agriculture', 'Issues & strategies for metals and rare earths'.

barriers in numerous institutions) could hinder the implementation of interdisciplinarity. Concerning the teaching approach, the students' participation in the group composition, applied pedagogy, assessment procedure and characteristics were identified as the most challenging issues of interdisciplinarity engineering education. Regarding the practice of PBL for engineering students sustainable development education, Guerra [2] provided empirical evidences and confirmed the relevance of the PBL for integrating sustainability education into engineering curricula by developing professional competences and expertise.

As to sustainability competences development, Quelhas et al. [3] identified the following eight key sustainability competences: systemic thinking, integrated problem-solving, interdisciplinary work, critical thinking, normative competence, competence of self-knowledge, strategic competence and contextualization and vision of the future (anticipatory thinking). In line with the results of Guerra [2], they confirmed by a comprehensive literature review that the practice of active learning (like PBL or case-based collaborative learning) is the most relevant pedagogical approach for development of sustainability competences.

Following the recommendations of Borrego and Cutler [4], the clear definition of the learning outcomes constructively adjusted to the curriculum is primordial for the good implementation of interdisciplinary sustainability education practice in engineering. They identified the following expected students' learning outcomes: contribution to the technical area, broad perspective, teamwork, and interdisciplinary communication skills.

3 METHODOLOGY

In this study, we use a mixed methodology, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches. The main advantage of this mixed approach is not only the opportunity to make the triangulation of our data but also the possibility to have a better explanation of what is behind the numbers of quantitative survey with the help of the findings from the qualitative study [5].

We have completed an online quantitative study with 79 fully completed questionnaire. Our questionnaire included closed questions with one exception of a multiple choice question about the competences. For the answers, we used a five points Likert scale (from 1='Not important at all / Strongly disagree' until 5='Very important / Strongly agree'). We asked students' perception on the three following thematic areas: sustainability courses' relevance, competences development and applied pedagogy.

For the qualitative study, we have designed the discussion guide in order to give us a broader insight about the motivations and experiences of the students. In the first section, we asked four open questions about the relevance of sustainability courses in engineering curricula, competences development and the possible impact of sustainability courses on students' future life. In the second section, we included five open question about students' perception concerning the relevance of applied

pedagogy and their suggestions of improvements. The group discussion was recorded and partially transcribed for facilitating our data analysis.

We analyzed our quantitative and qualitative data in three steps. In the first step, we analyzed the results of our quantitative survey by descriptive statistics. In the second step, we studied the textual data of our qualitative survey by a method of thematic analysis. In the last step, we combined the findings from our quantitative and qualitative studies.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Relevance of sustainability courses

Our results indicate an unexpected finding: 71% of the engineering students considered that their sustainability awareness and knowledge, before this course, was from very poor to average. Consequently, a clear majority of surveyed students (86%) think that these sustainability courses are really relevant in their engineering curriculum as seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1.: The perceived relevance and impact of sustainability courses on students' future professional and personal life (vertical axis in %)

Also, they clearly stated that sustainable issues are important or highly important for their future professional (58%) and personal life (53%). It is quite surprising that students consider sustainability development even more important in their professional future than in their personal life. During the group discussion, they also expressed that they would like to have more technical courses related to sustainability issues so as to convert their sustainable consciousness into practices and actions "...Our individual engagement is not sufficient ...we need to get

technical expertisein recycling method... [or] to be able to make correct choices [in our professional life]“. Many aspects they mentioned correspond indeed to product life cycle and sustainable innovation issues. Students have pointed out that their engineering training mainly focuses on how to use or create new technologies and does not really take into consideration in it the impacts of these technologies on sustainable development.

4.2 Competences development

Surprisingly, the high majority of students (75%) mentioned teamwork as the most developed competence during their interdisciplinary sustainability courses (see Figure 2). During the discussion, they explained that it was the first time during their studies that they had a project work in a team of ten instead of the usual small teams of 2 to 3 students. It was an interesting experience to learn how to distribute tasks in an efficient way, handle them with close deadlines, to manage well progress meetings and for some of them to experience leadership. Students namely mentioned the ripple effect of the motivation of the group.

The sustainability courses obviously developed their critical and reflective thinking for a more sustainable innovation. 65% of the students surveyed consider that they developed competencies in considering the environmental and social impact of their decisions.

It is interesting that nearly half of the surveyed students (49%) mentioned the development of their future thinking ability. From this result it is clear that students appreciate the inclusion of future perspectives into sustainability courses.

Although the interdisciplinary approach was present both in lectures and in the project work, only 29% of students consider that they have improved skills in this domain. One possible explanation comes from a student's statement: *'... the required level of scientific knowledge so as to cope with case studies was not very high...'*. Which may mean that the students consider that they would improve their interdisciplinary approach only if they increase at the same time their scientific knowledge in each discipline involved in the interdisciplinary context.

Fig.2. The perceived competences development of interdisciplinary sustainability courses. (% of students that mention the competence)

4.3 Applied pedagogy

The interdisciplinary sustainability courses includes lectures (20%) as well as project work (80%). The lectures are focusing on the global environmental impact of human living and the comparative energy cost of mobility both with quantitative analysis. The application of this mixed approach between a traditional lectures based on project based learning was considered by students as well balanced.

Students namely considered that the project based learning approach suited very well to sustainable issues. Furthermore, they pointed out that the size of the groups was well adapted to their team work even if it was not always easy to keep team members up to date to complete all the required tasks in time.

They highly appreciated having a huge autonomy and freedom in their projects and considered it as very profitable for developing their creativity.

During the discussion, students explained that their teamwork was particularly motivating due to the fact that they had the possibility to choose the thematic of their projects and to constitute their project team according to their interests (with students who wanted to work together or with students who were particularly interested by the same project thematic).

Students appreciated and realized the efficiency of collective learning from their own group but also from other groups. They mentioned that they learned much more in a short period of time than they would have alone.

Quantitative results are provided in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 : Students evaluation of the applied pedagogical approach

Nevertheless, they would have appreciated debates on each subjects. Debates on each subject that were initially planned via round tables, could finally not take place due to sanitary restrictions related to the COVID-19 pandemic.

5 CONCLUSION

Our findings enabled us to draw three main conclusions. First, the relevance of the project based learning approach practice for sustainability courses. It is particularly effective for raising the sustainability knowledge and awareness of the students as well as for developing their sustainability competences like critical and reflective thinking, teamwork or future thinking. The experience of working in a large team was strongly appreciated by the students. This collective learning offered them a huge autonomy and flexibility and it was perceived as a more motivating and engaging way to learn (comparing to their traditional lectures). The introduction of interdisciplinary courses was viewed valuable for understanding the interconnection between disciplines and for the comprehension of complex and open-ended sustainable development issues requiring expertise from different disciplines.

Secondly, and this is maybe the main result of our study, there is a growing demand of engineering students to include in their technical engineering courses a specific part dedicated to sustainability development issues. The students would like to acquire the needed sustainability skills and competences to tackle sustainability issues in their future professional life (in a similar way that they traditionally acquire technical knowledge and competences in engineering) in order to have an active contribution in achieving the sustainable development goals necessary for a better future.

Finally, the introduction of interdisciplinary sustainability courses is a challenging task that requires a relevant training of educators. The collaboration with other disciplines is not trivial for technical teachers who has prior experiences only in their own discipline. And in addition to this, it is not trivial either to acquire the expertise required in SD that will enable them to incorporate in their scientific courses the appropriate technical aspects related to sustainable issues.

As a future perspective, based on our findings, we would like to enhance the effectiveness of these sustainability courses by several major improvements like the further development of a specific collaborative learning practice between disciplines or the development of additional key sustainability competences.

REFERENCES

- [1] Van den Beemt, A., MacLeod, M., Van der Veen, J., Van de Ven, A., van Baalen, S., Klaassen, R., & Boon, M. (2020), Interdisciplinary engineering education: A review of vision, teaching, and support, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 109, No. 3, pp. 508-555.
- [2] Guerra, A. (2017), Integration of sustainability in engineering education, *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, Vol. 18, No. 3, pp. 436-454.

- [3] Quelhas, O. L. G., Lima, G. B. A., Ludolf, N. V. E., Meiriño, M. J., Abreu, C., Anholon, R., ... & Rodrigues, L. S. G. (2019), Engineering education and the development of competencies for sustainability, *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, Vol. 20, No. 4, pp. 614-629.
- [4] Borrego, M., & Cutler, S. (2010), Constructive alignment of interdisciplinary graduate curriculum in engineering and science: An analysis of successful IGERT proposals, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 99, No. 4, pp. 355-369.
- [5] Creswell, J.W., Plano Clark, V.L., Gutman, M.L. and Handson, W.E. (2003), *Advanced Mixed Methods Research Designs*, in A. Tashakkori and C. Teddlie (eds) *Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioral Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.